

D6.13

Quality of the produced olive oil

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Executive Summary

Deliverable D6.13 reports on the work developed under task 6.6 “Evaluation of the olive oil quality from the different management scenarios and study the impact of restoration on the overall quality of the product” during the Diagnostic pre-operational stage of SOIL O-LIVE project (first 18 months). The ultimate goal is to understand, at the end of the project, the relationship between farming practices, soil health, and olive oil quality and safety. This document describes the results obtained in the analysis of the quality parameters set by the International Olive Council (COI or IOC) for the olive oils obtained from the selected orchards.

From the 52 different orchards selected in Spain, Portugal, Morocco, Italy, and Greece, only 41 samples were received. The three different types of land management evaluated were: Traditional (TD), High-density (HD), and Organic (ORG). The lower production in the 2023 olive harvest season made it impossible to get samples from all orchards. Virgin olive oil was received only from 11 orchards, while olive oil production was performed at a laboratory scale through an Abencor® system for the remaining 30 orchards (which delivered frozen olives to the laboratory of analysis). Olive samples from two orchards from an experiment using biochar were also processed and analysed.

To determine the quality parameters of the produced oils, the samples were subjected to a batch of tests based on the following methods:

- Spectrophotometric investigation in the ultraviolet (COI/T.20/Doc. No 19., Rev. 5 (2019)).
- Determination of the total phenols’ content by spectrophotometric analysis (Folin-Ciocalteu method).
- Determination of fatty acid composition (COI/T.20/Doc. No 33. Rev. 1 (2017)).
- Determination of acidity (COI/T.20/Doc. No 34. Rev. 1 (2017)).
- Determination of peroxide value (COI/T.20/Doc. No 35. Rev. 1 (2017)).
- Determination of tocopherol and tocotrienol contents (ISO 9936:2016).

Methods are described in detail in document D6.12 “Quality analysis protocols and quality guidelines”.

Phenolic compounds are lower in high-density (HD) orchard oils compared to organic (ORG) and traditional (TD) oils, which have similar levels. TD oils have slightly higher oleic acid (C18:1) than ORG and HD, with HD having the lowest. Acidity is similar across all types, though TD oils show more variation. HD oils exhibit the widest range of peroxide values, including the highest, while ORG oils have the lowest. Tocols are similar across all types, but TD oils show the most variability. All oils meet EVOO/VOO criteria, but due to lab production, sensory panel testing is not recommended.

Table of Acronyms

COI/IOC – International Olive Council

ES – Spain

EU – European Union

EVOO – Extra Virgin Olive Oil

FC – Folin-Ciocaltêu

FFA – Free fatty acids

GR – Greece

HD – High-density

HPLC – High Performance Liquid Chromatography

IS – Internal Standard

IT – Italy

K_{xxx} – Specific extinction value

LVOO – Lampante Virgin Olive Oil

MR – Morocco

MRL – Maximum Residue Level

ORG- Organic

PT – Portugal

TAGs – Triacylglycerols

TD – Traditional

VOO – Virgin Olive Oil

ΔK – Variation in extinction

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document aims to disclose the results obtained from the evaluation of the different quality parameters set by the IOC for olive oils within the designated orchards. The investigation encompassed three different types of cultivation: traditional, high-density, and organic agriculture. The different tests performed were previously described in the document *D6.12 Quality analysis protocols and quality guidelines*. The objective of this study is to obtain information about the different quality parameters of the olive oil samples and to classify them into the different categories of olive oil based on the results.

1.2 Sampling

Out of the 52 olive orchards of the project, 41 samples from the different orchards were received from Spain, Portugal, Morocco, Italy, and Greece. Additionally, two samples were received from orchards where the soil was treated with biochar, which results will be discussed in a separate section. Details are available in Table 1.

Table 1. List of olive orchards from which olive oil samples were received

Traditional	High-density	Organic
ES-TD-01 Control	ES-HD-2	ES-ORG-4
ES-TD-01 Biochar*	ES-HD-3	ES-ORG-6
ES-TD-05 Control	ES-HD-8	ES-ORG-11
ES-TD-05 Biochar*	ES-HD-22	ES-ORG-12
ES-TD-07	ES-HD-40	ES-ORG-13
ES-TD-09	GR-HD-43	ES-ORG-14
ES-TD-15	MR-HD-25	GR-ORG-32
IT-TD-20	PT-HD-51	GR-ORG-33
IT-TD-50	PT-HD-52	GR-ORG-34
MR-TD-24	PT-HD-53	GR-ORG-45
MR-TD-26		GR-ORG-47
MR-TD-27		IT-ORG-18
MR-TD-28		IT-ORG-19
MR-TD-29		PT-ORG-42**
GR-TD-30		
GR-TD-31		
GR-TD-44		
GR-TD-46		
PT-TD-41		

*Biochar samples from the selected orchards will be compared in Section 3.2.

** Due to a mislabelling the sample in the previous version of this document was classified as PT-TD-42.

In summary, 79% of the expected samples have been received, as follows:

- Morocco – 6 olive oil samples out of 7 (**86 % of the expected samples**)
- Spain – 16 olive samples out of 16 have been received (**100 % of the expected samples**)
- Greece – 5 Oils and 5 olives out of 15 have been received (**75 % of the expected samples**)
- Portugal – 5 olive samples received (**100 % of the expected samples**)
- Italy – 4 olive samples out of 9 have been received (**44 % of the expected samples**)

From 11 orchards, olive oil was received, while raw fruit (olives) was received from the 30 remaining orchards. Unprocessed olives were also obtained from the orchards with biochar treatment. To obtain olive oil, the samples were processed using the ABENCOR procedure for olive oil extraction (malaxation: 30 °C, 30 min, no talc addition). This procedure has certain limitations, primarily because the capacity of the oil extraction machinery is very limited. The entire process is conducted manually, leading to increased processing time for samples compared to industrial-scale oil extraction. Consequently, to prevent degradation, the olives must be frozen in the laboratory before treatment in the Abencor® system. Additionally, the oils obtained through this method are not suitable for consumption due to the absence of standards in terms of food contact regulation and food safety protocols (both chemical and microbiological). Thus, these olive oils did not undergo panel test analysis.

2. Experimental

To determine the quality parameters of the produced oils, the samples were subjected to a batch of tests based on the following standardized methods (for details, see D6.12 document):

- Spectrophotometric investigation in the ultraviolet (COI/T.20/Doc. No 19., Rev. 5 (2019)).
- Determination of the total phenols' content by spectrophotometric analysis (Folin-Ciocalteu method).
- Determination of fatty acid composition (COI/T.20/Doc. No 33. Rev. 1 (2017)).
- Determination of acidity (COI/T.20/Doc. No 34. Rev. 1 (2017)).
- Determination of peroxide value (COI/T.20/Doc. No 35. Rev. 1 (2017)).
- Determination of tocopherol and tocotrienol contents (ISO 9936:2016).

3. Results

A total of 41 olive oil samples from different orchards were analysed. Additionally, olive oils from two orchards in which the soil was treated with biochar were also evaluated.

3.1 Oil extraction yield

The oil extraction yield was calculated using an Abencor® system in the conditions previously described (malaxation: 30 °C, 30 min, no talc addition). For Moroccan samples, the total oil content was calculated instead, using Soxhlet extraction, so the results are not comparable to the other. An overview of the yields obtained for the different oils is displayed in Table 2 according to the type of land management, and in Table 3 according to the country of origin.

The extraction yield was calculated using “cold” extraction conditions provided by the Abencor system used, not optimized to obtain the highest oil yield. Therefore, the reported values underestimate the actual fat content of the olives. For actual total fat content, Soxhlet extraction and/or Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) spectroscopy assays should be used instead.

Table 2. Extraction yield (%) by type of soil management

	TD	HD	ORG
Median (%)	10.0	9.4	8.2
Maximum value (%)	20.0	21.0	22.0
Minimum value (%)	2.1	6.1	1.2

The extraction yields obtained for the various oils based on soil management type are relatively similar. The median value was 10 % for TD orchards, 9.4 % for HD orchards, and finally 8.2 % for ORG orchards. The maximum value was virtually identical for all oils obtained: 20 % for TD and ORG, and 21 % for HD. The most notable difference lies in the lower yields obtained in TD and ORG oils (2.1 % and 1.2 % respectively) compared to the lower yield for HD oils (6.1 %).

Table 3. Extraction yield (%) by country

	Spain	Italy	Morocco*	Greece	Portugal
Median (%)	7.9	8.5	-	14.0	7.0
Maximum value (%)	12.7	14.0	-	22.0	8.1
Minimum value (%)	1.2	7.6	-	10.0	5.4

*No data available from the producer

When comparing the extraction yields by country, Greek olives showed the highest data, with a median value of 14.0 %. Extraction yields from Spain, Italy, and Portugal are comparable, ranging between 7.0 % and 8.5 %. There were no significant differences in performance observed between types of soil management across different countries.

3.2 Spectrophotometric investigation in the ultraviolet

This assay was made following the IOC method COI/T.20/Doc. No 19., Rev. 5 (2019). Spectrophotometric analysis in the ultraviolet range can yield insights into the quality of a fat, its preservation status, and alterations due to technological procedures. The data derived from this analysis offers valuable insights into the oxidation processes that oils may undergo. The outcomes are indicated through specific extinction values at 232 and 270 nm (K_{232} and K_{270}) and their variations in extinction (ΔK). Fig. 1 displays the data for each parameter by soil type management.

Fig 1. (a) K_{232} , (b) K_{270} , and (c) ΔK for the oils by type of soil management

To classify the oils, the IOC set limits by quality criteria, as indicated in Table 4.

Table 4. Quality criteria for oils by IOC

	EVOO*	VOO	LVOO
K_{270}	≤ 0.22	≤ 0.25	
K_{232}	≤ 2.50	≤ 2.60	
ΔK	≤ 0.01	≤ 0.01	

*EVOO: Extra Virgin Olive Oil; VOO: Virgin Olive Oil; LVOO: Lampante Virgin Olive Oil

According to the IOC standards, the K_{232} value for EVOO should be ≤ 2.50 . All the tested samples meet this requirement, as can be seen in Fig. 1a. For the K_{270} value, HD oils had a median of 0.12, ORG samples had 0.15, and TD yielded 0.17. In terms of median values, the oils obtained from the three types of soil management are classified as extra virgin olive oil (EVOO). However, upon closer examination of the maximum values (Fig. 1b), one sample from the TD orchards slightly exceeds the 0.22 threshold for K_{270} , thereby falling into the virgin olive oil (VOO) classification. Finally, the variation in extinction (ΔK) for the tested oils is under the requirements for their classification as EVOO. No pattern or significant difference has been detected among the three

types of soil management, as only one sample from traditionally managed orchards exceeds the requirements to be considered EVOO.

3.3 Determination of the total phenols' content by spectrophotometric analysis

The protocol for the extraction of phenolic compounds in olive oils will be the IOC method number 1, described in the document COI/T.20/Doc. No 29. Rev. 2 (2022), with small modifications. The spectrophotometric analysis will follow the Folin-Ciocalteu (FC) assay, also with small modifications¹.

This test provides information about the quantity of (poly)phenols in the processed oils. In this case, the higher levels of (poly)phenolic compounds in the samples the better. Fig. 2 represents the obtained data for the samples by type of soil management (HD, ORG, and TD).

Fig 2. Total phenols content (FC assay) for the oils, by type of soil management

The criteria set by the IOC indicate that oils can contain anywhere from 50 to 800 mg of gallic acid per kg of oil. Generally, all the processed oils fall within this specified range. However, upon closer examination, it becomes apparent that HD oils contain fewer (poly)phenols compared to ORG and TD oils, which exhibit similar levels to each other. The median values for HD, ORG, and TD oils are 253, 402, and 358 mg gallic acid/kg, respectively. It's noteworthy to mention the maximum values detected in ORG and TD oil samples, which are 1022 and 670 mg gallic acid/kg, respectively. Conversely, the minimum values detected for the three types of soil management are 85 for HD, 135 for ORG, and 161 for TD mg gallic acid/kg. The significant contrast between the maximum and minimum values suggests substantial differences among the samples.

3.4 Determination of fatty acid composition

The method used for determining the fatty acid composition in olive oils will follow the IOC method outlined in document COI/T.20/Doc. No 33, Rev. 1 (2017). This method involves converting the bound fatty acids of the triacylglycerols (TAGs) of vegetable fats and oils, along with, depending on the esterification method, the free fatty acids (FFA), into fatty acid methyl esters (FAME).

Fig. 3 represents the FAMES compositions for the different oils obtained from the three types of soil management.

Fig 3. FAMES composition for the oils by type of soil

Table 5. FAMES composition criteria set by IOC

	C14:0	C16:0	C16:1	C17:0	C17:1	C18:0
% fatty acids methyl esters	≤ 0,03	7,00 - 20,00	0,30 - 3,50	≤ 0,40	0,60	0,50 - 5,00
	C18:1	C18:2	C18:3	C20:0	C20:1	C22:0
% fatty acids methyl esters	55,00 - 85,00	2,50 – 21,00	≤ 1,00	≤ 0,60	≤ 0,50	≤ 0,20*

Adhering to the criteria established by the IOC and outlined in Table 5, the predominant fatty acids in oils should be C18:1 (oleic acid, 55 – 85 %), C16:0 (palmitic acid, 7 – 22 %), and C18:2 (Linoleic acid, 2.5 – 21 %). All the obtained oils conform to these standards. Oleic acid is quantified at a median of 75.2 %, 72.9 %, and 75.9 % in TD, ORG, and HD oils, respectively. Palmitic acid constitutes 16.4 % in HD oils, 13.0 % in ORG, and 12.3 % in TD oils. Linoleic acid is present at 10.9 % in HD oils, 7.2 % in ORG oils, and 6.6 % in TD oils. Interestingly, oils from the traditional type of soil management exhibit a relatively higher content of oleic acid compared to those obtained from HD and ORG soil management.

3.5 Determination of acidity

The protocol for the determination of the fatty acid composition in olive oils will be the IOC method described in the document COI/T.20/Doc. No 34. Rev. 1 (2017). The content of free fatty acids is expressed as acidity, calculated as the percentage of oleic acid as displayed in Fig. 4.

Fig 4. Acidity in % of oleic acid in oils per type of soil management

In regards to acidity, most of the oils can be classified as EVOO since their oleic acid percentage is below 0.8%. The median values for each type of soil management are 0.27% for HD, 0.25% for ORG, and 0.21% for TD oils. Two outlier values were recorded: one HD sample with 1.41% oleic acid and another sample from TD orchards with 0.97% oleic acid.

Table 6. Acidity classification criteria set by IOC

	EVOO*	VOO
Acidity (% oleic acid)	≤ 0.80	≤ 2.0

*EVOO: Extra Virgin Olive Oil; VOO: Virgin Olive Oil

3.6 Determination of peroxide value

The protocol for the determination of the peroxide value in olive oils will be the IOC method described in the document COI/T.20/Doc. No 35. Rev. 1 (2017). The peroxide value is the quantity of those substances in the sample, expressed in terms of milliequivalents of active oxygen per kilogram as displayed in Fig. 5.

Fig 5. Peroxide value in oils per type of soil management (meqO₂/kg)

The detected milliequivalent value of active oxygen per kg of oil for the oils from all three types of soil management consistently remained below 20.0 meq O₂/kg oil. This indicates that according to the IOC criteria (Table 7), all the tested oils are classified as EVOO for this test. Lower dispersion of data was observed in the ORG samples compared to the TD and HD samples. Despite meeting expectations, the HD samples displayed the highest data dispersion among all the tested samples. Median values were recorded at 1.3 meq O₂/kg oil for HD samples, 2.1 meq O₂/kg oil for ORG samples, and 2.40 meq O₂/kg oil for TD samples.

Table 7. Peroxide value classification criteria set by IOC

	EVOO*	VOO
Peroxide value (meq O ₂ /kg oil)	≤ 20,0	≤20,0

*EVOO: Extra Virgin Olive Oil; VOO: Virgin Olive Oil

3.7 Determination of tocopherol and tocotrienol contents

The protocol for the determination of tocopherol and tocotrienol contents in olive oils will be the method described in the standard ISO 9936:2016. This International Standard specifies a method for the determination of the contents of free α -, β -, γ -, and δ -tocopherols and tocotrienols (referred to jointly as tocols) in animal and vegetable fats and oils by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC).

The tocols content for the oils obtained from different soil management types is depicted in Figure 6. For the calculation, α -tocopherol has been used as the unique reference standard.

Fig 6. Tocols content in oils per type of soil management (mg/kg)

As an example, Fig. 7 represents the extracted chromatogram from a standard (black) compared to the obtained from one of the tested samples (pink).

Fig 7. Extracted chromatogram of α -tocopherol standard (black) and an olive oil sample (pink)

The ISO 9936:2016 method stipulates that the acceptable range of tocols in oils falls between 0 and 2220 mg/kg. All the samples tested meet this requirement, with median values for HD, ORG, and TD samples at 335, 325, and 382 mg/kg, respectively. There is some dispersion in the results from the various oils, with the most dispersed data observed from the traditional orchards, showing a maximum and minimum value detected of 648 and 94 mg/kg, respectively.

4. Discussion

A total of 41 samples were analysed under the conditions of the document *Quality analysis protocols and quality guidelines (D6.12)*. These samples originated from three different types of olive grove cultivation: traditional, high-density, and organic. Some of the samples were received as olive oil and the rest in the form of olives, which were extracted following the Abencor protocol available in the mentioned document D6.12.

Samples were individually tested for each quality parameter. The most significant findings presented previously in the results section are now summarized in Table 8.

In terms of phenolic compounds, it is evident that oils from HD soils have a lower polyphenol content than oils from ORG and TD soils, which show similar values on average. Regarding FAMES composition, it is observed that oils obtained from TD soils contain a higher amount of C18:1 than oils from ORG and HD soils, with the latter containing the least C18:1. The acidity of the oils, expressed as a percentage of oleic acid, is similar among the three types of cultivation, although a greater dispersion is observed in oils from TD soils.

Concerning peroxide values, oils from HD soil management exhibit a greater dispersion of results and the highest value obtained across all samples. However, oils from ORG cultivation show lower values. Oils from TD cultivation present some dispersion in values, but they are below those observed for HD. In terms of tocols content, all three types of oils behaved similarly, with median values being quite comparable. It is noteworthy that there is greater variability in these results in samples from TD cultivation, which have shown both the highest and lowest absolute values for this assay.

Despite all the oils analyzed being classified as EVOO or VOO, this cannot be certified until a tasting panel is conducted by specialists. The oils here produced are not suitable for consumption or to be tested as their food safety is not ensured.

An experiment with biochar has been evaluated. In two TD Orchards, the soil was partially treated using biochar. Control samples (untreated) and biochar-treated samples from these two orchards were tested. No remarkable differences were found between them in all the performed analyses.

Table 8. Summarized data

Oil extraction yield	Extraction yield (%)		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HD oils: 9.4 % • ORG oils: 8.2 % • TD oils: 10 % 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HD oils: 21 % • ORG oils: 20 % • TD oils: 20% 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HD oils: 6.1 % • ORG oils: 1.2 % • TD oils: 2.1 %
Spectrophotometric investigation in the ultraviolet	K270	K232	ΔK
	Median values by soil management types: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HD oils: 0.12 • ORG oils: 0.15 • TD oils: 0.17 1. HD, ORG and TD oils classified as EVOO based on median values, while one TD oil is considered VOO.	Compliance with IOC standards for K ₂₃₂ value: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EVOO: K232 ≤ 2.50 All the processed oils meet these criteria	Variation in extinction (ΔK) data: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EVOO: ΔK ≤ 0.01 All the processed oils meet these criteria
	All samples are considered EVOO except for one sample from the TD orchards, which is considered VOO.		
Determination of the total phenols' content by spectrophotometric analysis	Variation in (poly)phenol content among soil management types		
	Median values	Maximum values	Minimum values
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HD: 253 mg/kg, • ORG: 402 mg/kg • TD: 358 mg/kg 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HD: 843 mg/kg • ORG: 1022 mg/kg • TD: 670 mg/kg 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HD: 85 mg/kg • ORG: 135 mg/kg • TD: 161 mg/kg
HD oils contain fewer (poly)phenols compared to ORG and TD oils			
Determination of fatty acid composition (FAMES)	Quantification of fatty acids in processed oils (median)		
	Oleic acid: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TD: 75.5 %, • ORG: 72.9 % • HD: 75.9 % 	Palmitic acid: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HD: 16.4 % • ORG: 13.0 % • TD: 12.3 % 	Linoleic acid: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HD: 10.9 % • ORG: 7.2 % • TD: 6.6 %
Oils from traditional soil management have relatively higher oleic acid content compared to HD and ORG oils.			
Determination of acidity	All oils classified as EVOO due to oleic acid percentage below 0.8 %. Median values for acidity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HD oils: 0.27 % • ORG oils: 0.25 % • TD oils: 0.21 % 		

	Two samples surpassed the optimal range: one HD sample with 1.41% oleic acid and another sample from TD orchards with 0.97% oleic acid.		
Determination of peroxide value	<p>All oils from different soil management types consistently below 20.0 meq O₂/kg oil.</p> <p>Median values:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HD samples: 1.3 meq O₂/kg oil • ORG samples: 2.1 meq O₂/kg oil • TD samples: 2.4 meq O₂/kg oil 		
Determination of tocopherol and tocotrienol contents	Tocols content		
	Median values	Maximum values	Minimum values
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HD: 335 mg/kg • ORG: 325 mg/kg • TD: 382 mg/kg 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HD: 493 mg/kg • ORG: 514 mg/kg • TD: 648 mg/kg 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HD: 139 mg/kg • ORG: 110 mg/kg • TD: 94 mg/kg

5. References

- ¹ M. Pérez, I. Dominguez-López, and R. M. Lamuela-Raventós (2023). The Chemistry Behind the Folin–Ciocalteu Method for the Estimation of (Poly)phenol Content in Food: Total Phenolic Intake in a Mediterranean Dietary Pattern. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry* 71 (46), 17543-17553 DOI: 10.1021/acs.jafc.3c04022